

Maternal Factors Associated with a Successful Trial of Vaginal Birth after Cesarean Section

Muslima Firdaus Khan¹, Nabajyoti Saikia², Bandana Kurmi³, H. M. Shohail⁴

¹Post graduate trainee, Assam Medical College and Hospital (AMCH), Assam, India

²Assistant Professor, Assam Medical College and Hospital (AMCH), Assam, India

³Assistant Professor, Assam Medical College and Hospital (AMCH), Assam, India

⁴Medical Officer, Mandia BPHC, Assam, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Muslima Firdaus Khan

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: The rates of cesarean section (CS) have increased steadily all over the world in the past two decades. Trial of labour after cesarean delivery (TOLAC) is an alternative to repeat CS and vaginal birth after cesarean section (VBAC) is an accepted practice. Current evidence suggests that women who undergo repeated CS have significantly higher risk of maternal and perinatal morbidity compared with women who deliver vaginally after CS.

Aims and Objective: To detect the maternal factors associated with successful trial of vaginal birth after cesarean delivery.

Materials and Methods: This is a hospital based observational study done in Assam medical college, Dibrugarh, over a period of 1 year from March 2023 to February 2024.

A total of 54 women were eligible for TOLAC according to departmental protocol were included in this prospective study.

Results: There were 54 candidates for VBAC, Out of which 41 patients delivered vaginally. Trial of labour was successful in 75.93%.

Keywords: VBAC, TOLAC.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The rates of caesarean section (CS) have increased steadily all over the world in the past two decades. [1] Caesarean section is the most frequently performed surgery in the modern Obstetrics. Repeat caesarean section is the most common cause of high caesarean section rate globally. In India, the proportion of caesarean deliveries has dramatically increased to 17% (2015-16) and 21.5% (2019-21) from just 3% in 1992-93. [2]

Vaginal birth after cesarean section (VBAC) is the term applied to women who undergo vaginal delivery following cesarean delivery in a prior pregnancy. Woman with a previous caesarean birth, the decision regarding planned mode of birth in a subsequent pregnancy will be influenced by many factors, including previous experience of a vaginal birth, desire to achieve a vaginal birth, feelings about the previous caesarean birth, and family considerations (including an easier recovery). [3]

Women undergoing CS may face health risks including haemorrhage, blood transfusion, anaesthesia-associated complications and surgical risks [4],

infection, Deep vein thrombosis, uterine rupture [3,5,6] pelvic adhesions, morbidly adherent placenta, bladder injury and increased cumulative hysterectomy rates [7,8]. The increasing number of women with a previous CS is an urgent matter and should be given close attention by clinicians and policymakers. All pregnant women with a previous caesarean section should be given a trial of labour.

Major complications associated with TOLAC include scar dehiscence, uterine rupture, hysterectomy but successful TOLAC is associated with less blood loss, significantly lower risk of neonatal morbidities, reduces chances of adherent placenta and a shorter hospital stay with a more rapid recovery [9,10,11]. TOLAC should be considered among women if there are no contraindications and successful TOLAC can be safely achieved for both mother and infant in most cases. [12] Globally, TOLAC is considered a reasonable and safe option.

A World Health Organization (WHO) survey in Latin America identified that women with singleton cephalic pregnancy with prior caesarean section,

despite their smaller pool, were the greatest contributors to the overall cesarean section rate. [13]

Materials and Methods

Study Place: Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh

Type of Study: Hospital based observational study

Duration of Study: One Year from March 2023 to February 2024.

Study Population: The study will comprise of all patients with history of one previous Caesarean section.

Sample Size: considering the proportion of women with successful TOLAC as 84% [14], the sample size for the present study is calculated to be 54 with 95% confidence and marginal error of 10%.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with previous history of one Cesarean section.
- Patient giving informed consent for VBAC and for the study.
- Pregnant women with singleton foetus.
- Fetus with vertex presentation.
- Had a previous Caesarean section and scheduled for trial of labour after caesarean delivery (TOLAC).
- Clinically estimated fetal weight $\leq 3\text{kg}$
- Adequate pelvis on clinical assessment
- Spontaneous labour in absence of maternal or fetal compromise.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Preterm labour, gestational age < 37 weeks

- Two or more Cesarean section
- Contraindications for vaginal birth.
- History of other uterine incision such as myomectomy.
- Women with one previous Caesarian section with recurrent causes.
- Women with previous upper segment cesarean section
- Post term pregnancy.

Data Collection: From records kept in the labour room and operation theatre.

Statistical Analysis: After delivery, the collected data on admission were statistically analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS; Chicago, IL, USA), version 16. Numerical variables were presented as mean and standard deviation (\pm SD), while categorical variables were presented as number and percentage. Chi-square (X^2) test was used for the comparison between groups with regard to qualitative variables, while using unpaired student t)-test was used for the comparison as regards quantitative variables. [8]

Ethical Approval and Informed Consent: Ethical clearance taken from Institutional Ethics Committee (H) of Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh. Written and informed consent has been taken from the participants.

Results and Observation: Fifty-four (54) women were eligible for TOLAC according to departmental protocol and were included in this study after informed consent.

This is a pie diagram showing TOLAC was successful in 75.93% (41) women and unsuccessful in 24.07% (13).

Figure 1: Outcome

Booking visit: Out of 54 study patients who were given a trial of labour after a caesarean section, 36 patients had antenatal checkup in Assam Medical College (Booked), Dibrugarh and rest 18 patients were showing their antenatal checkup elsewhere (Unbooked).

Table 1:

Booking Status	Successful		Unsuccessful		p value*
	n	%	n	%	
Booked	29	70.73	7	53.85	0.260
Unbooked	12	29.27	6	46.15	
TOTAL	41	100.00	13	100.00	

***Chi-square Test; The p-value is not significant at 5% level of significance**

The mean age of women included in this study was 27.44± 2.56 years in successful group and 28.15 ± 3.53 years in unsuccessful group.

Figure 2: Mean Age Wise Distribution

Table 2: Age Wise Distribution

Age (in years)	Group	Successful		Unsuccessful		p value*
		n	%	n	%	
≤20		0	0.00	0	0.00	0.697
21–25		11	26.83	2	15.38	
26–30		25	60.98	9	69.23	
31–35		5	12.20	2	15.38	
>35		0	0.00	0	0.00	
TOTAL		41	100.00	13	100.00	

***Fisher Exact Test; The p-value is not significant at 5% level of significance**

In this study, all the recruited patients were divided into 5 groups based on their age. Around 60.98 % of the total study patients belong to the age group of 26 – 30 years had successful VBAC and around 15.38 % belongs to the age group more than 31 year had unsuccessful TOLAC. We also performed

analysis by subgroup for BMI. BMI at admission before delivery of women with successful VBAC were lower than those of woman with failed VBAC. Mean BMI was significantly lower in successful TOLAC (24.02±0.83)kg/m² compared to unsuccessful group (26.79±1.22)kg/m².

Table 3:

Body mass index	Successful		Unsuccessful	
	Mean	±S.D.	Mean	±S.D.
Height (cm)	158.88	2.56	154.69	2.02

Weight (Kg)	60.63	2.63	64.08	2.53
BMI (Kg/m²)	24.02	0.83	26.79	1.22

Gestational Age at Presentation: The gestational age was calculated as per Nageli’s formula provided the prior menstrual cycles were regular. The patients whose prior menstrual cycles were irregular, gestational age was calculated from the dating scan. The study population was divided into two groups depending on the gestational age.

Table 3:

Gestational (in weeks)	Age	Successful		Unsuccessful		p value*
		N	%	n	%	
<39		29	70.73	2	15.38	<0.001*
≥39		12	29.27	11	84.62	
TOTAL		41	100.00	13	100.00	

***Fisher Exact Test; The p-value is significant at 5% level of significance**

Out of 54 patients, around 31 patients presented at near term at around 39 weeks of gestational age, out of which 70.73% patient had successful VBAC.

The effect of gestational age on the mode of delivery was identified in this study, and it was found to be statistically significant.

Presenting complaints: In my study, the patients were admitted with the following complaints given in chart below. 25 patients were admitted with spontaneous of labour i.e, pain abdomen, 13 patients with draining per vaginum, 9 patient with decrease fetal movement and 6 patient with bleeding per vaginum.

Figure 3: Chief Complications

Bishop score at admission: In the study, all the patients recruited underwent pre vaginal examination and Bishop Score was assigned. These scores were grouped into 2 categories and it was found that around 66.67 % had a BISHOP score more than 6. After the data analysis, it was found that Bishop score of more than 6, is a predicting factor for successful vaginal delivery in a patient with previous caesarean section.

Table 4:

Outcome		Successful		Unsuccessful		p value*
		n	%	n	%	
Bad	≤6	5	12.20	13	100.00	<0.001*
Good	>6	36	87.80	0	0.00	
Total		41	100.00	13	100.00	

***Fisher Exact Test; The p-value is significant at 5% level of significance**

Discussion

For all patients who meet the trial eligibility requirements and have had a previous cesarean section, TOLAC is thought to be one alternative that need to be offered. The perinatal morbidity and death linked to repeat cesarean sections will be reduced by this technique. Following factors were analysed in this prospective observational study like booking visit, effect of maternal age, gestational age at presentation, pre pregnancy BMI, presenting complain on admission in labour room, bishop score.

54 patients, who were consented for trial of labour, were recruited for the study and out of which 41 patients had a successful vaginal delivery and 13 patients underwent emergency repeat cesarean section. In a study done by Ibrahim A. Abdelazim and colleagues, 122 women were eligible for TOLAC, and TOLAC was successful in 88 patients (72.13%). [8]

Using bivariable and multivariable analyses, a retrospective cohort study conducted in Philadelphia by Sindhu K. Srinivas et al. on women undergoing TOLAC in 17 community and university hospitals, admitted between 1996 and 2000, discovered that advanced maternal age, or more than or equal to 35 years, is associated with a lower likelihood of a successful VBAC.[15]

In this study around 60.98 % of the total study patients belong to the age group of 26 – 30 years had successful VBAC and around 15.38 % belongs to the age group more than 31 year had unsuccessful TOLAC. Hammoud et al. conducted a cohort research wherein all mothers with singleton pregnancies were recruited between 1988 and 2002. The study evaluated the outcome of TOLAC with gestational age and discovered that the success rate of VBAC is low for advanced gestational age [16].

In this study, the effect of gestational age on the mode of delivery was identified, and it was found to be statistically significant. Landon et al. (17) reported a significantly lower success rate of vaginal birth after cesarean section (68.4%) in obese (BMI ≥ 30) than non-obese women (76.9%), in the present study, there was statistical difference in the pre pregnancy BMI in both groups of Emergency repeat LSCS and vaginal delivery.

In this study, TOLAC was successful in increased Bishop Score (more than 6) on admission compared to unsuccessful group. After the data analysis, it was found that Bishop Score of more than 6, is a predicting factor for successful vaginal delivery in a patient with previous cesarean section.

One hundred (100) women were included in Raja and colleagues' study, and concluded that increasing scores correlated with an increasing probability of vaginal birth after cesarean section [18].

Conclusion

It has been demonstrated that women who undergo successful VBAC have lower short-term and long-term morbidity. Conversely, women who are unsuccessful following TOLAC have the highest morbidity. For this reason, Trial of labour after CS should be considered in women who have no contraindications that are relatively few, classical or T-shaped uterine incision after appropriate discussion. Identifying the best candidates using factors available to the obstetrician can increase VBAC success rate and minimize maternal morbidity.

References

1. Betrán AP, Ye J, Moller AB, et al. The Increasing Trend in Caesarean Section Rates: Global, Regional and National Estimates: 1990-2014. *PLoS One* 2016; 11:e0148343.
2. Lips ICF. National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5): 2019-21 India. Mumbai Int Inst Popul Sci IIPS. 2021;
3. Dodd JM, Crowther CA, Huertas E, Guise JM, Horey D. Planned elective repeat caesarean section versus planned vaginal birth for women with a previous caesarean birth. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* [Internet]. 2013; (12). Available from: <https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD004224.pub3/abstract>
4. Villar J, Carroli G, Zavaleta N, Donner A, Wojdyla D, Faundes A, et al. Maternal and neonatal individual risks and benefits associated with caesarean delivery: multicentre prospective study. *Bmj*. 2007; 335(7628):1025.
5. Liang J, Mu Y, Li X, Tang W, Wang Y, Liu Z, et al. Relaxation of the one child policy and trends in caesarean section rates and birth outcomes in China between 2012 and 2016: observational study of nearly seven million health facility births. *bmj* [Internet]. 2018; 360. Available from: <https://www.bmj.com/content/360/bmj.k817.abstract>
6. Marshall NE, Fu R, Guise JM. Impact of multiple cesarean deliveries on maternal morbidity: a systematic review. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2011; 205(3):262-e1.
7. Paré E, Quiñones JN, Macones GA. General Obstetrics: Vaginal birth after caesarean section versus elective repeat caesarean section: assessment of maternal downstream health outcomes. *BJOG Int J Obstet Gynaecol*. 2006 Jan; 113(1):75–85.
8. Abdelazim IA, Elbiaa AA, Al-Kadi M, Yehia AH, Nusair BMS, Faza MA. Maternal and obstetrical factors associated with a successful trial of vaginal birth after cesarean section. *J Turk Ger Gynecol Assoc*. 2014; 15(4):245.
9. Oboro V, Adewunmi A, Ande A, Olagbuji B, Ezeanochie M, Oyeniran A. Morbidity associated with failed vaginal birth after cesarean

- section. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.* 2010 Sep; 89(9):1229–32.
10. Quinlan JD, Murphy NJ. Cesarean delivery: counseling issues and complication management. *Am Fam Physician.* 2015; 91(3):178–84.
 11. Patel RM, Jain L. Delivery after previous cesarean: short-term perinatal outcomes. In: *Seminars in perinatology* [Internet]. Elsevier; 2010; 272–80. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0146000510000315>
 12. Sentilhes L, Vayssière C, Beucher G, Deneux-Tharaux C, Deruelle P, Diemunsch P, et al. Delivery for women with a previous cesarean: guidelines for clinical practice from the French College of Gynecologists and Obstetricians (CNGOF). *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2013; 170(1):25–32.
 13. Betrán AP, Gulmezoglu AM, Robson M, Merialdi M, Souza JP, Wojdyla D, et al. WHO Global Survey on Maternal and Perinatal Health in Latin America: classifying caesarean sections. *Reprod Health.* 2009 Dec; 6(1):18.
 14. Li YX, Bai Z, Long DJ, Wang HB, Wu YF, Reilly KH, Huang SR, Ji YJ. Predicting the success of vaginal birth after caesarean delivery: a retrospective cohort study in China. *BMJ open.* 2019 May 1; 9(5):e027807.
 15. Srinivas SK, Stamilio DM, Sammel MD, Stevens EJ, Peipert JF, Odibo AO, et al. Vaginal birth after caesarean delivery: does maternal age affect safety and success? *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.* 2007 Mar; 21(2):114–20
 16. Hammoud A, Hendler I, Gauthier RJ, Berman S, Sansregret A, Bujold E. The effect of gestational age on trial of labor after Cesarean section. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2004 Mar 1; 15(3):202–6.
 17. Landon MB, Leindecker S, Spong CY, Hauth JC, Bloom S, Varner MW, et al. The MFMU Cesarean Registry: factors affecting the success of trial of labor after previous cesarean delivery. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2005; 193:10 16–23.
 18. Raja JF, Bangash KT, Mahmud G. VBAC scoring: Successful vaginal delivery in previous one caesarean section in induced labour. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2013; 63:1147–51.